

Utilizing XGBoost Classifier for Detecting Abnormal Patterns in Longitudinal Response Time Data

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Introduction

Detecting fraudulent behavior in high-stakes testing is crucial for maintaining integrity. Existing methods often rely on prior identification of compromised items or dishonest test-takers, limiting their real-world applicability. A more robust, assumption-free approach is needed to effectively address this challenge and ensure the security.

Purpose

- Detect abnormal patterns in test items without prior assumptions, utilizing longitudinal response time information.
- Evaluate XGBoost classifier's performance in detecting these abnormal response time patterns, offering a new approach to enhance test security in adaptive testing environments.

Dataset

The study utilized data from a large-scale computerized adaptive test conducted over 13 months, administering 226 pretest items to 58,302 examinees with an average of 4,240 responses per item. This yielded a dataset of 226 rows and 53 features, based on weekly average response times.

A manual labeling scheme was employed to categorize items based on their response time trajectories, yielding three distinct classes:

- (1) Consistent Decrease (22 items)
- (2) Partial Decrease (51 items)
- (3) Inconsistent Decrease (153 items)

Figure 1. Response Time Trends for Multiple Items

Methods

- The XGBoost classifier was employed to model the relationship between response time features and target outcomes.
- Data preprocessing steps included:
 - Mean imputation for handling missing values
 - Stratified 80/20 train-validation splitting
 - Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE) for class balancing

Methods (cont'd)

- Grid search was performed to enhance model performance, focusing on the following parameters:
 - Boosting rounds: [50, 100, 150]
 - Tree depth: [3, 4, 5]
 - Learning rate: [0.01, 0.05, 0.1]
 - Subsample ratio: [0.6, 0.8, 1.0]
 - L1 regularization: [0.01, 0.1, 1]
 - L2 regularization: [0.01, 0.1, 1]

This comprehensive tuning approach aimed to optimize the model's performance.

- Following initial modeling and tuning, an ensemble method was implemented to potentially improve classification performance:
 - Combined three classifiers: XGBoost, Support Vector Classifier (SVC), and Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP)

This approach aimed to leverage the strengths of different algorithms and compare the results with the initial methods applied by using XGBoost with and without oversampling.

Table 1. Classification Results Before Oversampling

Category	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
Consistent Decrease	0.00	0.00	0.00	3
Partial Decrease	0.25	0.12	0.17	8
Inconsistent Decrease	0.79	0.94	0.86	35
Accuracy			0.74	46
Macro Avg	0.35	0.36	0.34	46
Weighted Avg	0.64	0.74	0.68	46

Table 2. Classification Results Before Oversampling

Category	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
Consistent Decrease	0.25	0.33	0.29	3
Partial Decrease	0.25	0.38	0.30	8
Inconsistent Decrease	0.83	0.71	0.77	35
Accuracy			0.63	46
Macro Avg	0.44	0.47	0.45	46
Weighted Avg	0.69	0.63	0.66	46

Table 3. Ensemble Method Results

Category	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
Consistent Decrease	0.33	0.33	0.33	3
Partial Decrease	0.43	0.38	0.55	8
Inconsistent Decrease	0.97	0.71	0.88	35
Accuracy			0.76	46
Macro Avg	0.58	0.63	0.58	46
Weighted Avg	0.83	0.76	0.78	46

Figure 2. Confusion Matrix – Before Oversampling

Figure 3. Confusion Matrix – After Oversampling

Figure 4. Confusion Matrix – Ensemble Methods

Results

The study compared three approaches: XGBoost without oversampling, XGBoost with SMOTE oversampling, and an ensemble method combining XGBoost, SVC, and MLP.

1. XGBoost without oversampling:

- Showed poor performance on minority classes.
- High accuracy (0.74) mainly due to good performance on the majority class (Inconsistent Decrease).
- Confusion matrix shows it misclassified most minority class instances.

2. XGBoost with SMOTE:

- Improved overall performance, especially for minority classes.
- Accuracy decreased slightly to 0.63, but F1-scores for minority classes improved significantly.
- Confusion matrix shows better detection of Consistent and Partial Decrease cases.

3. Ensemble method (XGBoost + SVC+MLP):

- Best overall performance across all metrics.
- Highest accuracy (0.76) and balanced performance across all classes.
- Confusion matrix shows improved classification for all categories, especially minority classes.
- Substantial improvement in Partial Decrease detection compared to other methods.

Discussions and Conclusions

- XGBoost classifier effectively identifies items with abnormal response time patterns.
- High accuracy achieved without relying on prior identification of compromised items or dishonest test-takers.
- Provided approach demonstrates potential for proactive, continuous monitoring and real-time anomaly detection across various testing environments, enhancing test security and integrity.

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